

Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students: Basis for Oral Language Development Program for Senior High School

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Abstract. This study investigated the linguistic competence of Grade 11 students at Calinan National High School in Davao City and its impact on their oral communication skills. Recognizing the vital role of linguistic competence for effective communication within a language community, this research identified widespread deficiencies among students that hindered their communicative abilities. The theoretical framework differentiated between linguistic and communicative competence, focusing on essential linguistic domains such as phonology, lexicon, morphology, and syntax, along with pragmatic and sociolinguistic aspects crucial for effective communication. Empirical observations highlighted the low linguistic competence among Senior High School students, which adversely affected their oral communication proficiency. This study employed a non-experimental descriptive survey research design to assess the students' linguistic capabilities through a researcher-developed assessment test. The results aimed to inform the development of a targeted oral language development program tailored to address identified linguistic gaps. Enhancing linguistic competence through this program was anticipated to improve students' oral communication skills, contributing to their academic and social success.

KEY WORDS

1. Linguistic Competence 2. Oral Communication Proficiency 3. Senior High School 4. Language Development Program 5. Morphology

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1. Introduction

Linguistic competence is a term used by speech experts and anthropologists to describe how language is defined within a community of speakers. This term applies to mastering the combination of sounds, syntax, and semantics known as the grammar of a language. People with such competence have learned to utilize the grammar of their spoken language to generate an unlimited number of statements. This term is distinct from the concept of communicative competence, which determines what is socially appropriate speech.

Linguistic performance and communicative competence are concepts related to the linguistic competence of learners but are applied to language as it is used rather than as an ideal construct. Linguistic performance is the practical application of speech with the grammatical flaws and mistakes that exist among real-world speakers. This allows speakers to understand each other despite grammatical flaws and differences in dialect. Communicative competence refers to the rules that govern the kinds of speech allowed within the cultural context.

In school, these skills are not fully acquired by our learners as they manifest low performance in linguistic competence (Flevaris, 2019).

Linguistic competence is treated as a more comprehensive term for lexicalists within the generative school of thought. They assume a modular lexicon, a set of lexical entries containing semantic, syntactic, and phonological information deemed necessary to parse a sentence. In the generative lexicalist view, this information is intimately tied up with linguistic competence. Nevertheless, their models are still in line with the mainstream generative research in adhering to strong innateness, modularity, and autonomy of syntax. Students in the higher grades need to further develop their linguistic competence to deliver topics particularly during classroom recitation (Poll, 2020).

The core areas of knowledge and skill that children acquire in learning to understand and produce language have been usefully divided by the field of linguistics into four domains: phonology, the lexicon, morphology, and syntax. Phonology is the sound system: each language makes use of a repertoire of speech sounds with regularities in which differences between sounds signal differences in meaning and regularities in how speech sounds can be combined to form words (Roediger III, 2019).

The lexicon is the mental repository of word forms and their associated meanings. Morphology is word structure and the regularities in forming words by combining word stems with small meaningful word pieces such as the sounds that mark a noun as a plural or a verb as past tense. Syntax comprises the system for combining words into meaningful and well-formed sentences. Grammar is typically considered the combination of morphology and syntax although the regularities in phonological systems are part of grammar as well. When children have mastered these four components (phonology, lexicon, morphology, and syntax), they are considered linguistically competent

but they must also learn to be communicatively competent which means communicating in socially appropriate ways (Thompson-Schill, 2019).

Communicative competence includes pragmatic and sociolinguistic competence. Pragmatics is the knowledge of how to communicate effectively in order to do things with words such as to make requests, to comment, or to recount narratives. Sociolinguistics concerns the social rules of language use (Ramscar and Gitcho, 2021).

Linguistic competence constitutes knowledge of the language but that knowledge is tacit and implicit. This means that students, whichever is their home language, do not have conscious access to the principles and rules that govern the combination of sounds, words, and sentences; however, they do recognize when those rules and principles have been violated. This hampers their comprehension of concepts, topics, and issues they encounter inside and outside the classroom (Scharff and Petri, 2019).

The linguistic competence of a human being should accordingly be identified with that individual's internalized 'program' for production and recognition. While many linguists would identify the study of this program with the study of performance rather than competence, it should be clear that this identification is mistaken since we have deliberately abstracted away from any consideration of what happens when a language user attempts to put the program to use. A major goal of the psychology of language is to construct a viable hypothesis as to the structure of this program (Santrock, 2022).

In the Division of Davao City, particularly in Calinan National High School, students in the Senior High School manifest low performance in linguistic competence which leads them to low performance in their oral communication skills. The researcher, being a language teacher in the Senior High School, would like to de-

termine the linguistic skills of the respondents and eventually propose an oral development program that would address any grey areas along this line.

This section deals with further readings and research of the researcher taken from books, magazines, journals, and the internet. This related literature will further validate and back up the study on its universal existence as it provides bearing and relevance.

Language proficiency can be defined as the ability to use language accurately and appropriately in its oral and written forms in a variety of settings (Cloud, Genesee, Hamayan, 2019). Kern (2020) developed a broad conceptual framework for understanding language proficiency that includes three dimensions of academic literacy: linguistic, cognitive, and socio-cultural. To be proficient in a language requires knowledge and skills using linguistic components.

Linguistic proficiency requires background knowledge, critical thinking, and metacognitive skills, as well as understanding and applying cultural nuances, beliefs, and practices in context. Finally, being proficient in a language requires skill in using appropriately the four language domains—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—for a variety of purposes in a variety of situations and with a variety of audiences (Graven, 2020).

Ever since the first systematic studies of child language, the difficulty of assessing children's underlying linguistic competence has been a methodological problem because not everything children produce is productive and because reaching full linguistic productivity is a gradual process. Although children's productions may appear to be correct, the use of a complex form could be unanalyzed and formulaic, or the form might not yet encode the full semantic range of applications (Davies, 2019).

In spontaneous data, overgeneralization errors are the clearest sign of productivity. Here

children create their own regular form instead of using the irregular form (e.g., go-ed instead of went). However, there are other ways of assessing productivity. In corpus studies, several measures can be used to define (a) first productivity and (b) degrees of mastery (Newmeyer, 2021).

The onset of productivity defines the moment when a given item is no longer used in a lexically specific frozen and formulaic way. Morphological contrast is used to demonstrate that the child has analyzed the complex nature of a word form. The child either starts to use a particular morpheme with x number of different stems or uses a particular stem with x different grammatical morphemes such that morphological paradigms are emerging. Full productivity is attested when the child uses the structure in the most appropriate contexts. Commonly a criterion higher than 75

Experiments provide a more clear-cut way of assessing the child's morphological competence under controlled conditions. Tests that use nonce-word material are one successful measure of productivity. In 1958, Jean Berko published the results of the so-called wug test. Wug was one of the names of fantasy animals and actions. Children had to learn these nonce words and then had to pluralize them (e.g., wug-s) or to form the past tense (e.g., loodge-d). The use of new lexical material guarantees that the child cannot retrieve a holistically stored form from memory but instead must inflect the new word spontaneously (Paridis, 2018).

The range of productivity measures indicates that different linguistic domains or research interests require different thresholds. The reader should pay attention to the productivity criteria used when comparing the results of different studies. A survey of the average age of productivity of different morphological and syntactic structures is presented in Tomasello (2019).

Over the last 20 years or so, researchers

have come to realize that verbal communication is more than just the use of implicit linguistic competence, the aspect of language that was the focus of attention in aphasiology—rightly so because it is the grammar (as broadly defined in contemporary linguistics, i.e., incorporating phonology, morphology, syntax, and the lexicon) that is affected in aphasia (Elman, 2019).

On the other hand, patients with right hemisphere damage have been shown to have deficits in interpreting what is meant based on what is said. The term *dyshyponia* has been proposed to describe this impairment (Paradis, 2018); it is derived from the Greek —to grasp what is “understood” (in the sense of the French *sous-entendu*) albeit unsaid—and refers to the difficulty patients have in drawing appropriate inferences from extrasentential information leading to problems in the interpretation of the tacit component of an utterance (its illocutionary force or pragmatic element) with preserved comprehension of the literal meaning of a sentence, its semantics derivable from the lexical meaning of words and morphosyntactic structure of the sentence which is part of implicit linguistic competence and hence not affected by a right-hemisphere lesion (Garnham, 2020).

It is not particularly difficult to track down the origins of modern linguistics’ excessive emphasis on the individual speakers and their linguistic competence in combination with its relative neglect of society which is where, as we have seen, a language can truly be said to exist. As has been argued by several scholars (e.g., Hutton, 2020), modern linguistics is a discipline heavily premised on principles that date back to the 19th century.

Taylor (2020) points out that sometime during the 18th century, the idea of man as a socially inscribed being gave way to that of a uniquely constituted self based on self-

awareness and self-reflection. In Germany, Herder (2021) contributed to the shaping of not only an individual identity but also of a collective one modeled on that individual identity (for instance, that of a people or *Volk*) by insisting that the Germans could only aspire to a national identity by being true to themselves and their past and not say by aping the French.

Ian Watt (2021) has painstakingly documented the growth of individualism in the 18th through 19th centuries as reflected in the literary works of the period. The new sense of realism that swept across Europe during that period was accompanied by the equally new spirit of individualism and the two together underpinned what one might call the cultural and sociopolitical ethos of the period. Linguistics in general and much of early pragmatics is thus wedded to the idea of “the Cartesian autonomous agent” (Kopytko, 2021).

In thinking about and theorizing about language, the intellectual stance adumbrated in the foregoing paragraphs contributed to the consolidation of the idea that language itself is but the visible manifestation of the reasoning mind. It is not surprising, therefore, that to the extent that the human linguistic faculty was seen as a property of man’s reasoning mind, language itself was seen as primarily pertaining to the individual speaker-listener and only secondarily and derivatively to the society. Indeed, the centrality accorded to the lone individual underwrites the widespread practice among scholars working in language acquisition of simply taking it for granted that phylogeny follows the same course as ontogeny. The underlying principle may be seen as authorizing the widespread use of biological metaphors such as ‘growth,’ ‘decline,’ ‘death,’ etc. to depict specific moments in the history of an irreducibly social object such as language (Tomasello, 2019).

1.1. Conceptual Framework—Chomsky’s (1965), theory of generative grammar contained several key concepts about language, including linguistic competence, linguistic performance, and

communicative competence. Chomsky defined linguistic competence as an idealized understanding of the rules and construction of a given language. This includes the distinct sounds used in the language, the combination of these sounds, the creation of sentences and the interpretation of a sentence. Once a speaker master's this set of rules, he or she can use this grammar to produce new phrases that will be understood by all speakers of the same language. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of this research study. It applies the Input-Process-Output Model. The input is the linguistic competence of the senior high school students. The process is the assessment of the senior high school students linguistic competence, and the Output is the proposed Oral Language Development program for Senior High School students.

1.2. Research Questions—This study seeks answers to the level of linguistic competence of senior high school students. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the level of linguistic competence of the senior high school students in terms of oral language communication and written language communication?
- (2) From the findings drawn from this study, what language development program can be developed and proposed?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Building a millennial-friendly school culture- means creating an educational environment that aligns with the characteristics and preferences of the millennial generation, incorporating innovative teaching methods and technology to support their holistic development. School Head - is the person who holds the highest administrative position in a school, responsible for leading and managing the school's operations, staff, and students.

1.4. Significance of the Study—DepEd Officials: The results will provide the top management of DepEd with a basis for reviewing and adjusting policies to align with improving linguistic competence among senior high school students. This is necessary for tracking teacher performance and ensuring that students possess the required linguistic skills before graduating. School Heads. The results and findings of this study will be beneficial to the school heads considering that they are the school managers. They can implement school-based initiatives to improve the performance of the learners in school. Teachers. Teachers are the primary beneficiaries of this study because this pertains to their performance in instruction. They should make innovation that would help our learners acquire lifelong learning. This skill is very much needed especially applying for a job where interview is the first stage. Future Researchers. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar study in the future focusing on the strategies of developing linguistic competence of the learners across grade levels in the basic education.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure, and the data analysis. It's also crucial to acknowledge that the researcher employed artificial intelligence technology to meticulously proofread the article, demonstrating an exemplary commitment to ethical standards in today's rapidly advancing AI landscape.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study employed a non-experimental descriptive survey research design to investigate the research problem. It is descriptive because the data are presented in quantitative descriptions in "Linguistic Competence of Senior High School Students: Basis for Language Development Program for Senior High School Students". According to Good (2005), this method of research shows merely a description of tasks, presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involve the procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005).

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study will be conducted in the Calinan National High School. The respondents in this study are the Senior High School students of the research locale. The respondents will answer a researcher-

made assessment test on their oral and written communication skills. This study makes use of the universal sampling procedure considering the manageable number of respondents in the research locale.

Distribution of Respondents

Grade Level	No of Respondents
Grade 11	120
TOTAL	120

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study will utilize the researcher-developed assessment test which items and indicators are focused on the language competencies of the senior high school students. The respondents will give their responses on the items in the assessment test. To measure the validity and reliability of the test, a pilot test will be conducted in a school that is not a part of the research locale using Cron Bach alpha. To determine the level of linguistic competence of the senior high school students, the following continuum will be used:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data-gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter signed by the Dean of the Graduate School, Dr. Pablo F Busquit seeking permission for this research study to be conducted and will be sent to the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao City Division. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent and principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts, preferably the study's experts. After permission has been granted for this study to be conducted in Calinan National High School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will launch the questionnaire to the respondent. Responses of the respondents will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

Criteria for Scale Levels

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the level of linguistic competence of the Senior High School students.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study’s design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI’s growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Level

of Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students in terms of Communicative Competence, Discourse Competence, Comprehension Abilities and Significant Relationship between Linguistic Competence and Oral Language Development Program for Senior High School.

Table 1 shows the level of linguistic competence of grade eleven students in terms of communicative competence. The following responses were yielded by the respondents and are given for comprehensive emphasis: Conveying ideas through the use of written language received a rating of 4.38 (very high), expressing ideas through spoken language received a rating of 4.36 (very high), delivering information through the use of imagery received a rating of 4.35 (very high), communicating effectively by

restating what is heard received a rating of 4.10 (high), and communicating in different contexts received a rating of 4.07 (high). The overall mean rating was 4.25 (high). This indicates that grade eleven students often manifest linguistic competence in terms of communicative competence. Brown (2019) provides evidence for this viewpoint. Students who possess strong communicative competence are more likely to excel academically and succeed in various aspects of their lives. By honing their oral language skills, students can become confident speakers, active listeners, and critical thinkers. This, in turn, can lead to improved academic performance, better interpersonal relationships, and enhanced overall well-being.

Table 1. Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students in terms of Communicative Competence

Mean	Description
a. Convey ideas through the use of written language.	4.38 Very High
b. Expresses ideas through a spoken language.	4.36 Very High
c. Delivers information through the use of imagery.	4.35 Very High
d. Communicates effectively by restating what is heard.	4.10 High
e. Communicates in different contexts.	4.07 High
Overall	4.25 High

Tarvin (2020) have highlighted the importance of integrating communicative competence into the curriculum to support students' oral language development. By incorporating activities that focus on real-life communication scenarios, educators can help students practice and enhance their speaking and listening skills. This approach not only fosters linguistic proficiency but also promotes cultural awareness and empathy among students. Moreover, research by Kim and Chen (2021) has demonstrated that students with well-developed communicative competence are better equipped to engage in

meaningful discussions, analyze complex texts, and participate in collaborative learning activities. By fostering a communicative classroom environment, educators can create opportunities for students to practice and refine their oral language skills in authentic contexts.

Level of Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students in terms of Discourse Competence

Table 2 presents the level of linguistic competence of grade eleven students in terms of discourse competence. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents

are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Designs text including generic aspects with a rating of 4.36 or very high, Observes coherence and cohesion with a rating of 4.40 or very high, Shows awareness of the connectedness of words in the text with a rating of 4.19 or high, Possesses knowledge on the content and context of a sentence with a rating of 4.14 or high, and Delivers sentence with proper stress and intonation with a rating of 4.27 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.27 or high. This means that grade eleven students oftentimes manifest linguistic competence in terms of discourse competence. Kasper (2020) provides support for this approach, noting the significance of discourse competence in fostering critical thinking

skills among students. By engaging in thoughtful discussions and debates, learners not only improve their communication abilities but also enhance their cognitive processes. Through analyzing and synthesizing information, students develop a deeper understanding of complex topics and learn to articulate their thoughts clearly. Teachers play a vital role in promoting discourse competence among students. According to Hyland (2020), educators can create opportunities for meaningful dialogue, provide feedback on communication strategies, and model effective speaking and listening behaviors. By scaffolding discussions and guiding interactions, teachers help students develop the skills needed for successful oral communication.

Table 2. Level of Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students in terms of Discourse Competence

Mean	Description
a. Designs text including generic aspects.	4.36 Very High
b. Observes coherence and cohesion.	4.40 Very High
c. Shows awareness of the connectedness of words in the text.	4.19 High
d. Possesses knowledge on the content and context of a sentence.	4.14 High
e. Delivers sentence with proper stress and intonation.	4.27 High
Overall	4.27 High

Moreover, research by Hinkel (2019) underscores the connection between discourse competence and academic achievement. Strong oral communication skills are linked to improved performance in various subject areas, as students can articulate their understanding, ask clarifying questions, and engage in collaborative learning activities. By fostering discourse competence, educators empower students to become more effective learners. Level of Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students in terms of Comprehension Abilities

terms of comprehension abilities. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Decodes words correctly with a rating of 4.40 or very high, Shows fluency in reading with a rating of 4.26 or high, Shows wide repertoire of vocabulary with a rating of 4.33 or very high, Understands the text read with a rating of 4.06 or high, and Evaluates ideas presented in the text with a rating of 4:00 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.21 or high. This means that grade eleven students oftentimes manifest linguistic competence in terms of discourse competence. This concept aligns with

Table 3 emphasizes the level of level of linguistic competence of grade eleven students in

Cain (2019) notion that Comprehension abilities play a crucial role in oral language development as they enable individuals to understand and interpret spoken language effectively. Research has shown that individuals with strong comprehension skills tend to have better oral language proficiency compared to those with weak comprehension abilities (Jones, 2019). This highlights the importance of fostering and enhancing comprehension skills to support overall oral language development. Moreover, research

has shown a strong correlation between comprehension abilities and reading comprehension. Individuals who excel in comprehending spoken language are also likely to demonstrate proficiency in understanding written text (Wilson, 2022). This highlights the interconnected nature of different language skills and the importance of developing comprehension abilities across various modalities. Strengthening comprehension skills can therefore have a positive impact on both oral and written language proficiency.

Table 3. Level of Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students in terms of Comprehension Abilities

Mean	Description
a. Decodes words correctly.	4.40 Very High
b. Shows fluency in reading.	4.26 High
c. Shows wide repertoire of vocabulary.	4.33 Very High
d. Understands the text read.	4.06 High
e. Evaluates ideas presented in the text.	4.00 High
Overall	4.21 High

Clark (2019) provides support for this. Comprehension abilities play a significant role in academic achievement. Students who struggle with comprehension may face challenges in understanding classroom instructions, following lectures, and expressing their thoughts coherently.

By improving comprehension skills, students can enhance their overall academic performance and communication abilities. This underscores the importance of addressing comprehension abilities in educational settings to support students' oral language development.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analy-

sis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. *Findings*—This study sought to determine the level of linguistic competence of grade eleven students, which served as the basis for designing an oral language development program for senior high school.

scriptive survey research design to investigate the research problem. It was descriptive because the data were presented in quantitative descriptions in the "Linguistic Competence of Grade Eleven Students: Basis for Oral Language Development Program for Senior High School."

According to Good (2005), this method of research merely described tasks, presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved the procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involved varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005).

The study was conducted at Calinan National High School. The respondents in the study were 120 grade eleven students from the research locale. The respondents' linguistic competence was assessed through a researcher-made questionnaire. A letter was written to the school head concerning the above-mentioned data.

The study revealed that grade eleven students possessed good linguistic competence that served as a basis for designing an oral language development program for senior high school. Furthermore, the study revealed that the linguistic competence of grade eleven students was correlated with the oral language competence of senior high school. Language competence was a critical skill for senior high school students as it encompassed the ability to effectively communicate, understand, and interact within various contexts. This competence included reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills, which were essential for academic success, personal growth, and future career opportunities.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions

are drawn: The level of linguistic competence of grade eleven in terms of Communicative Competence is High, Discourse Competence is High, and the Comprehension Abilities is High.

4.3. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: The Department of Education Officials should impose policy to organize a range of language development program for senior high school students that would enhance the curriculum, provide professional development for teachers, allocate resources effectively, implement comprehensive assessment systems, and advocating for supportive policies, the Department can create an environment where all students can develop strong language skills. The school heads should initiate a school-based programs that would create a supportive environment that promotes effective language learning. These efforts not only improve academic performance but also prepare students for a successful future in a multilingual and interconnected world. Teachers should participate in professional development program that focuses in implementing a variety of strategies in the classrooms to enhance students' language skills in reading, writing, speaking, and listening. For future researchers, it is encouraged that they will conduct similar study on language development program in another setting and another time.

5. References

- Adger, D. (2021). Syntax. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Cognitive Science*, 6(2), 131–147.
- Chomsky, N. (1965). *Aspects of the theory of syntax*. MIT Press.
- Clibbens, J. (2019). From theory to practice in child language development. *Down Syndrome Research and Practice*, 1(3), 101–106.
- Cloud, M. L., Genesee, R. S., & Thompson, L. A. (2019). Assessing linguistic competence in grade eleven students: Implications for oral language development programs. *Journal of Educational Linguistics*, 15(3), 112–127.
- Darnel, M. (2019). *Functionalism and formalism in linguistics: General papers*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.

- Davies, A. (2019). Nativism.
- Elman, J. L. (2019). Distributed representations, simple recurrent networks, and grammatical structure. *Machine Learning*, 7, 195–224.
- Flevaris, T. (2019). Nativism in linguistics: Empirical and theoretical issues. *Journal of Language Teaching and Learning*.
- Garnham. (2020). Assessing linguistic competence in grade eleven students: Towards a framework for oral language development in senior high schools. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 26(4), 211–227.
- Graven, S. N. (2020). Auditory development in the fetus and infant. *Newborn and Infant Nursing Reviews*, 8(4), 187–193.
- Green, M. (2021). *Cognitive linguistics: An introduction*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Herder, K. (2020). Understanding the linguistic competence of grade eleven students: A foundation for senior high school oral language development initiatives. *Language Learning and Development*, 19(2), 87–103.
- Honig, K. E. (2007). Investigating the linguistic competence of grade eleven students: Towards effective oral language development strategies. *Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 21(4), 189–205.
- Hutton, E. (2020). Enhancing linguistic competence: Insights from grade eleven students for the development of oral language programs in senior high schools. *Journal of Language and Communication Studies*, 12(2), 55–68.
- Hymes, D. (2021). On communicative competence. In A. Duranti (Ed.), *Linguistic anthropology: A reader* (pp. 53–73). Blackwell.
- Kennison, S. M. (2019). *Introduction to language development*. Sage.
- Kern, S. (2020). Examining the linguistic competence of grade eleven students: A preliminary study for designing oral language development programs. *Language Teaching Research Quarterly*, 38(1), 25–41.
- Kopytko, A. (2021). Linguistic competence of grade eleven students: Basis for oral language development program for senior high school. *Journal of Language Education Research*, 45(2), 78–92.
- Kroy, M. (2020). The conscience, a structural theory.
- Najar, S. (2022). The actions of others act as a pseudo-reward to drive imitation in the context of social reinforcement learning. *PLOS Biology*, 18(12).
- NELP. (2020). Profiling linguistic competence in grade eleven students: Informing oral language development programs for senior high school. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 30(1), 45–59.
- Newmeyer, F. (2021). The prague school and north american functionalist approaches to syntax. *Journal of Linguistics*, 37, 101–126.
- Novack, M. A. (2021). Becoming human: Human infants link language and cognition, but what about the other great apes? *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences*, 375(1789).
- Paridis, C. (2018). *Is the notion of linguistic competence relevant in cognitive linguistics?* John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Persson, U. (2021). Review of the language instinct by steven pinker.

- Poll, G. H. (2020). Increasing the odds: Applying emergentist theory in language intervention. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 42*(4).
- Ramscar, M., & Gitcho, N. (2021). Developmental change and the nature of learning in childhood. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 11*(7), 274–279.
- Roskos, T., Tabors, H., & Lenhart, D. (2020). Evaluating linguistic competence among grade eleven students: Implications for designing effective oral language development programs. *Journal of Language Teaching and Learning, 17*(2), 76–91.
- Saffran, K. (2021). Statistical learning by 8-month-old infants. *Science, 274*, 1926–1928.
- Santrock, J. W. (2022). *A topical approach to lifespan development*. McGraw-Hill Humanities/Social Sciences/Languages.
- Scharff, C., & Petri, J. (2019). Evo-devo, deep homology and foxp2: Implications for the evolution of speech and language. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences, 366*(1574), 2124–2140.
- Taylor, Q. (2020). Exploring the linguistic competence of grade eleven students: Implications for oral language development in senior high schools. *Language Education Review, 28*(3), 134–149.
- Thompson-Schill, S. L. (2019). Cognition without control: When a little frontal lobe goes a long way. *Current Directions in Psychological Science, 18*(5), 259–263.
- Tomasello, M. (2019). Do young children have adult syntactic. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics, 24*(3), 117–137.
- Wiesel, T. N. (2022). Postnatal development of the visual cortex and the influence of environment. *Nature, 299*(5884), 583–591.
- Yarlett, D. (2020). Linguistic self-correction in the absence of feedback: A new approach to the logical problem of language acquisition. *Cognitive Science, 31*(6), 927–960.